

PROPOSED PROBLEMS

by

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(i) Solve the following equations:

$$1) S^k(x) + S^k(y) = S^k(z), \quad k \in \mathbb{Z}, x, y, z \in \mathbb{Z}$$

where S' is the Smarandache function and $S(-n) = -S(n)$

$$2) \frac{4}{n} = \frac{1}{S(x)} + \frac{1}{S(y)} + \frac{1}{S(z)}, \quad n > 4$$

$$3) \frac{5}{n} = \frac{1}{S(x)} + \frac{1}{S(y)} + \frac{1}{S(z)}, \quad n > 5$$

$$4) S^{S(y)}(x) = S^{S(x)}(y)$$

$$5) S\left(\sum_{k=1}^n x_k^u\right) = S^u\left(\sum_{k=1}^n x_k\right), \quad u \in \mathbb{Z}$$

$$6) S^y(x) - S^t(z) = S^{y-t}(x-z)$$

$$7) \sum_{k=1}^n S^m(x_k) = \sum_{k=n}^{2n} S^m(x_k)$$

$$8) 2S(x^4) - S^2(y) = 1$$

$$9) S\left(\frac{x+y+z}{3}\right) + \frac{S(x)+S(y)+S(z)}{3} = \frac{2}{3}\left[S\left(\frac{x+y}{2}\right) + S\left(\frac{y+z}{2}\right) + S\left(\frac{z+x}{2}\right)\right]$$

$$10) S(x_1^{x_1}) \cdot S(x_2^{x_2}) \dots S(x_n^{x_n}) = S(x_{n+1}^{x_{n+1}})$$

$$11) S(x_1^{x_2}) \cdot S(x_2^{x_3}) \dots S(x_{n-1}^{x_n}) = S(x_n^{x_1})$$

$$12) S(x) = \mu(y), \quad \text{where } \mu \text{ is the Möbius function}$$

$$13) S^2(Q_n) = \sum_{Q_{n-1}|Q_n} \dots \sum_{Q_2|Q_3} \sum_{Q_1|Q_2} \mu^2(Q_1)$$

$$14) S(x) = B_y, \quad \text{where } B_y \text{ is a Bernoulli number}$$

$$15) S(x+y) (S(x) - S(y)) = S(x-y) (S(x) + S(y))$$

$$16) S(x) = F_y , \quad \text{where } F_y \text{ is a Fibonacci number}$$

$$17) \sum_{k=1}^n S(k^p) = \sum_{k=1}^n S^p(k)$$

$$18) \sum_{k=1}^n S(k) = S\left(\frac{n(n+1)}{2}\right)$$

$$19) \sum_{k=1}^n S(k^2) = S\left(\frac{n(n+1)(2n+1)}{6}\right)$$

$$20) \sum_{k=1}^n S(k^3) = S\left(\frac{n^2(n+1)^2}{4}\right)$$

$$21) \sum_{k=1}^n k(S(k)!) = (S(n+1))! - 1$$

$$22) \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{S(k)S(k+1)} = \frac{S(n)}{S(n+1)}$$

(ii) Solve the system

$$\begin{cases} S(x) + S(y) = 2S(z) \\ S(x) \cdot S(y) = S^2(z) \end{cases}$$

(iii) Find n such that n divides the sum

$$1^{S(n-1)} + 2^{S(n-1)} + \dots + (n-1)^{S(n-1)} + 1$$

(iv) May be written every positive integer n as

$$n = S^3(x) + 2 S^3(y) + 3 S^3(z) \quad ?$$

(v) Prove that

$$\begin{aligned} |S(x) + S(y) + S(z)| + |S(x)| + |S(y)| + |S(z)| &\geq \\ &\geq |S(x) + S(y)| + |S(y) + S(z)| + |S(z) + S(x)| \end{aligned}$$

for all $x, y, z \in \mathbb{Z}$

(vi) Find all the positive integers x, y, z for which

$$(x+y+z) + S(x) + S(y) + S(z) \geq S(x+y) + S(y+z) + S(z+x)$$

(vii) There exists an infinity of prime numbers which may be written under the form

$$P = S^3(x) + S^3(y) + S^3(z) + S^3(t) \quad ?$$

(viii) Let $M_1, M_2, \dots, M_n$ be finite sets and $a_{ij} = \text{card}(M_i \cap M_j)$, $b_{ij} = S(a_{ij})$. Prove that $\det(a_{ij}) \geq 0$ and $\det(b_{ij}) \geq 0$.

(ix) Find the sum

$$\sum_{Q_{n-1}|Q_n} \dots \sum_{Q_2|Q_3} \sum_{Q_1|Q_2} \frac{1}{S^2(Q_1)}$$

(x) Prove that

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{S^2(k) - S(k) + 1} \text{ is irrational}$$

(xi) Find all the positive integers x for which

$$S\left(\left[\frac{x^{n+1} - 1}{(n+1)(x-1)}\right]\right) \geq S\left(\left[x^{\frac{n}{2}}\right]\right)$$

where $[x]$ is the integer part of x.

(xii) There exists at least a prime between $S(n)!$, and $S(n+1)!$?

(xiii) If $\sigma \in S_n$ is a permutation, prove that

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{\sigma(k)}{S^{m+1}(k)} \geq \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{k^m}$$

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